

ANTENATAL DIAGNOSIS OF BLADDER EXSTROPHY: CONTEMPORARY APPROACHES AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

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Abstract. *Bladder exstrophy is a rare congenital anomaly characterized by non-closure of the lower part of the anterior abdominal wall and the bladder wall, which leads to exposure of the mucous membrane of the posterior wall of the bladder. Antenatal (prenatal) diagnostics of this pathology is of key importance for timely planning of pregnancy management, delivery, as well as for the development of tactics of neonatal surgical correction. This article considers modern methods of antenatal visualization of bladder exstrophy, differential diagnostics and approaches to counseling expectant parents.*

Keywords: *developmental defect, exstrophy, cloaca and urogenital sinus, Fetal magnetic resonance imaging.*

Introduction. Bladder exstrophy (BE) is a rare but clinically significant malformation of the genitourinary system, occurring with a frequency of about 1 case per 30-50 thousand births. The defect occurs due to a disruption in the formation of the lower part of the anterior abdominal wall and the cloacal membrane in the early stages of embryogenesis (approximately 4-10 weeks of gestation) [3,4,7,15,17,29]. Without timely diagnosis and treatment planning, this defect can lead to serious urinary dysfunction, urogenital and sexual dysfunction, as well as cosmetic and psychological problems.

It is important to note that this developmental defect is characterized by the absence of the anterior abdominal wall and the anterior wall of the bladder, as well as divergence of the pubic symphysis. The mucous membrane of the bladder prolapses through the defect of the anterior abdominal wall. The orifices of the ureters, from which urine is constantly released, are located in the lower part of the exposed mucous membrane. The umbilical cord flows low into the upper edge of the defect of the anterior abdominal wall [10,15,26,46].

The findings indicate that exstrophy defects of the lower urinary tract are divided into classic bladder exstrophy and cloacal exstrophy. In boys, bladder exstrophy is combined with a split urethra (epispadias). Bladder exstrophy in girls is accompanied by a split clitoris, a split or absence of the urethra, as well as adhesions of the labia majora and minora [4,8,11,22,30].

In the literature, bladder exstrophy is most often described in combination with epispadias, although there are reports of isolated damage to the bladder wall when its neck and urethra are formed. Such pathology is called incomplete exstrophy, or anterior vesical fistula. With incomplete exstrophy, there is no pathology of the genitals [1,12,39]. The most severe and rare form of the defect is cloacal exstrophy, in which the splitting extends not only to the urogenital area, but also to the terminal section of the intestine.

Exstrophy of the bladder as a congenital malformation was first described by Schenk von Grafenberg in 1597. In 1780, Chaussier first used the term "exstrophy". References to bladder exstrophy were found on Assyrian tablets made 2000 years BC [1,7,23]. The incidence of bladder

exstrophy is 0.25-0.5 per 10 thousand newborns. The ratio of classical bladder exstrophy in boys and girls is 3:1 [6,14,21,43]. With bladder exstrophy, there are associated congenital anomalies - inguinal hernias (in 56% of boys, in 15% of girls), cryptorchidism (20%), colorectal anomalies (1.8%), etc. [3,4,11,24,35,36]. Bladder exstrophy can be part of the OEIS complex (omphalocele, extrophy, imperforate anus, spinal defects).

It should be emphasized that prenatal diagnostics of bladder exstrophy is possible already during the first screening examination at 11-14 weeks of pregnancy, when the bladder cavity normally begins to fill with urine. Visualization of the bladder is necessarily included in the standard protocols of prenatal screening studies.

Antenatal diagnostics allows for timely identification of bladder exstrophy, determination of the degree of the defect and preparation of a team of specialists - obstetricians, neonatal surgeons, urologists, anesthesiologists - for the necessary intervention immediately after birth.

Embryology and pathogenesis. The formation of the bladder is associated with the development of the cloaca and urogenital sinus. During normal embryogenesis, the cloacal membrane merges and closes, the abdominal wall and a full-fledged wall of the bladder are formed. With exstrophy, this process is disrupted, which leads to a hernia-like protrusion of the mucous membrane of the posterior wall of the bladder outward. Understanding the stages of organ formation is important for interpreting ultrasound findings and early detection of defects.

Standard ultrasound examination (2D ultrasound): the optimal time to detect structural anomalies, including bladder exstrophy, is traditionally considered to be the second trimester of pregnancy (16–20 weeks), when detailed anatomical screening is performed [30]. Studies show that already at this time, it is possible to suspect the absence of normal bladder filling and anomalies in the lower anterior abdominal wall [33,45]. In particular, in bladder exstrophy, it is not possible to visualize a clearly defined bladder on repeat scans, and an abnormal echo-positive structure may be observed in the suprapubic region [35,45,48].

3D/4D ultrasound technologies allow for improved visualization and three-dimensional assessment of the defect, while Doppler ultrasonography facilitates differential diagnosis with other abdominal hernias such as omphalocele or gastroschisis [11,16,35].

Fetal magnetic resonance imaging (MRI): MRI has proven to be a valuable adjunctive diagnostic tool in cases of complex or unclear ultrasound findings [29,34]. Due to the high contrast of soft tissues, MRI improves the accuracy of differentiation of anatomical structures and allows for clear visualization of the pelvic bones, external genitalia, and assessment of the degree of involvement of adjacent structures [34]. This is especially important for planning neonatal correction and assessing the prognosis.

Limitations of MRI include cost, availability, and duration of the procedure, but in specialized centers this method is increasingly used when complex malformations are suspected [14,15].

Additional diagnostic methods: if it is necessary to exclude genetic syndromes or chromosomal abnormalities, invasive methods (amniocentesis, chorionic biopsy) and non-invasive genetic tests (NIPT) are used [1,4,9,15,42]. This allows for a comprehensive assessment of the fetus's condition and planning further tactics for pregnancy management, delivery and postnatal treatment.

It has been demonstrated that during antenatal examination, it is important to differentiate bladder exstrophy from other defects of the abdominal wall and lower abdomen.

Omphalocele and gastroschisis: bladder exstrophy, these pathologies are characterized by hernial protrusions with intestinal loops or other organs in the umbilical region [43]. A characteristic sign is the presence or absence of a membrane (sac) in the case of omphalocele, and in gastroschisis - the exit of the intestine into the amniotic cavity without a membrane. In these pathologies, the bladder can usually be visualized separately [29].

Cloacal exstrophy: more severe defect in which not only the bladder is affected, but also other structures (rectum and reproductive organs). Diagnosis is based on more pronounced and complex anomalies, as well as the absence of the normal structure of the posterior urethra, often the complete absence of a normal anus [32,35,40].

It is widely accepted that bladder exstrophy may be combined with other congenital defects (skeletal anomalies, genital defects, anorectal malformations). Antenatal diagnostics is often accompanied by invasive methods (amniocentesis, chorionic biopsy) to exclude chromosomal abnormalities and other genetic syndromes [33].

When confirming the diagnosis of bladder exstrophy, it is important to provide parents with complete information about the nature of the pathology, treatment methods, and prognosis for the child's quality of life. Often there is a need for a multidisciplinary approach involving a pediatric urologist, neonatal surgeon, geneticist, and psychologist. Shared decision-making on the place and method of delivery (in a specialized center, with the possibility of neonatal correction) increases the chances of a successful outcome [9].

The presence of an antenatal diagnosis of bladder exstrophy allows timely preparation for surgical correction of the defect in the early neonatal period. Primary surgeries are aimed at closing the bladder and abdominal wall, and subsequently reconstructive interventions may be required to correct the function of the bladder and genitals. The prognosis for life is generally favorable, but the quality of life and functional outcomes depend on the degree of the defect, the presence of concomitant anomalies and the timeliness of correction [4,9,41].

Discussion. Prenatal ultrasound data on bladder exstrophy were recognized by the presence of a solid convex formation in the lower abdominal wall, the absence of visualization of the bladder and normal volume of amniotic fluid. Minor features include low insertion of the umbilical cord, widened iliac crests, normal kidneys, small penis, and epispadias. However, prenatal diagnosis of this condition is not straightforward and only a few cases have been reported in the literature. In a retrospective review, the correct diagnosis was made in only 3 of 17 cases. If it can be demonstrated that the mass originates from the bladder, then theoretically the diagnosis will be easier [42,45,46].

There is growing consensus that the umbilical arteries arise from the external iliac arteries and pass along both sides of the bladder before entering the umbilical cord. They are clearly visible on color Doppler ultrasound, so the umbilical arteries can be considered a good landmark for the bladder. In this case, we found that the umbilical arteries were adjacent to a solid mass in the lower abdomen of the fetus. We inferred the origin of the solid mass to be the bladder and confirmed the diagnosis of bladder exstrophy. Since there was no visible bladder on gross examination, this is not a typical case of bladder exstrophy, and the solid mass on prenatal ultrasound is consistent with an open surface of the abdominal defect. Recognition of the intrafetal umbilical arteries provides clues to bladder exstrophy anomalies, even when they are atypical, as in this case [30,35].

The differential diagnosis includes all other anterior abdominal wall defects such as omphalocele, gastroschisis, and cloacal exstrophy. In the first two defects, there is a protruding sac or herniated bowel, but a normally filled bladder should be visible in the pelvic cavity. In

omphalocele, the umbilical arteries may run inferior to the mass and the umbilical vein runs through a hepatic herniation. Depiction of the umbilical vein within the bulging mass allows the diagnosis of omphalocele to be made. The diagnosis of cloacal exstrophy is often difficult but can be made in more complex anomalies involving the gastrointestinal tract and spine [39,40,43]. A persistent urachus may resemble a normal bladder and complicate the diagnosis. However, long-term follow-up shows that the structure is constant in size and shape and does not have any voiding episodes, excluding the possibility of a normal bladder [5,31].

It is worth highlighting that prenatal diagnosis of bladder exstrophy should be made in the presence of the following features: (1) a solid mass in the lower anterior fetal abdomen, (2) an invisible fetal bladder, (3) normal amniotic fluid volume, (4) low-set umbilical cord insertion, (5) normal fetal kidneys, (6) flared iliac bones, (7) umbilical arteries located near a bulging mass protruding from the lower abdominal wall, and (8) malformation of the external genitalia. Awareness of the intrafetal umbilical arteries provides valuable information about the origin of the solid mass in the lower fetal abdomen.

Conclusion: It can be concluded that antenatal diagnosis of bladder exstrophy is an important step in the comprehensive management of this congenital defect. Modern imaging techniques, combined with genetic research and a multidisciplinary approach, allow timely determination of the delivery and neonatal treatment strategy. This significantly improves the child's outcomes, reduces the risk of complications and contributes to an improved quality of life in the future.

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